

MANAGEMENT OF THE INTEGRATED COACHING MODEL IN IMPROVING THE PERFORMANCE OF PRIVATE UNIVERSITY LECTURERS

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Abstract

The basis for conducting research is related to the phenomenon that occurs today, namely the suboptimal performance of lecturers in carrying out their duties and responsibilities, which has implications for the low achievement of the quality of the Tri Dharma of Higher Education. The general purpose of the research is to obtain a clear description, formulate and analyze the management of an integrated coaching model in improving lecturer performance in Private Universities (Universitas Komputer Indonesia dan Universitas Garut). The specific purpose of the research is to know, study, and analyze more deeply about planning, organizing, directing and supervising. What are the supporting and inhibiting factors, how to overcome obstacles and how the lecturers' work results after the implementation of the integrated coaching model. The theories used are; management theory from Nickels, McHugh and McHugh, integrated coaching model theory from Jonathan Passmore, and performance theory from Bernardin and Russell. The research approach uses qualitative, with a descriptive method. Data collection techniques through interviews, observations, and documentation studies. Data analysis uses Miles & Huberman's interactive techniques. The results of the study showed; Planning is prepared in a visionary manner by prioritizing logic, clarity and reality that occurs. The organization is arranged neatly, well and correctly. The briefing is arranged in a coordinated, communicative and continuous manner. Supervision is prepared in a continuous, useful, comprehensive and accurate manner. There are supporting and inhibiting factors from the aspect; Human resources, budget, infrastructure and commitment in realizing the program. Efforts made; strategy formulation, making ideas and policies to overcome management obstacles of the Integrated Coaching Model. The management of the integrated coaching model in improving the performance of lecturers of Private Universities has been in accordance with the management functions of Nickels, McHugh and McHugh and is based on a value system (Achmad Sanusi) sourced from the Qur'an and Hadith, so that it has produced lecturers who have good and optimal performance in terms of work productivity, work quality, initiative to seek strategies, cooperation and success in solving problems.

Keywords: Management, Integrated Coaching Model, Lecturer Performance.

INTRODUCTION

The Tri Dharma of Higher Education are the three basic components that must be carried out and achieved by every university in Indonesia. This is stated in Law No. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System in article 20 paragraph 2 and Law No. 12 of 2012 concerning Higher Education in article 1 paragraph 9, where in both articles it is mandated that every Higher Education has the obligation to organize the Tri Dharma of Higher Education which includes; education and teaching, research, and community service.

According to a source from deepublish (2020), currently the implementation of the Tri Dharma of Higher Education is still not in accordance with the expected targets. These indications can be seen from inadequate facilities and infrastructure in universities, then in terms of university management that is not well organized, in terms of the quality of universities that are still lacking, and the performance of educators and education personnel is not optimal. The performance of educators, in this case educators in universities or lecturers, has three areas of work which include; in the field of Education and Teaching, in the field of Research, and in the field of Community Service (PkM) or better known as the Tri Dharma of lecturers.

In relation to the Tri Dharma carried out by lecturers, especially in the field of research and community service. Based on the results of a preliminary study through the sinta3.kemdikbud.go.id and forlap.kemdikbud.go.id pages which are information and statistical portals about universities in Indonesia, it is known that the participation of lecturers in researching and carrying out community service in several Private Universities, especially in the scope of Region IV (West Java and Banten) is still considered lacking/not optimal. As seen in the following tabulation:

Table 1: Performance Data of Lecturers of Several Private Universities Region IV Based on Research Fields

Code	Name of PTS	Verified Authors SINTA	REVIEW PDDIKTI	(%)
031037	Universitas Gunadarma Depok	678	1560	43,46
041031	Universitas Nasional Pasim	39	109	35,78
041023	Universitas Sali Al-Aitaam	32	95	33,68
041042	Universitas Subang	69	155	44,52
041043	Universitas Majalengka	173	296	58,45
041047	Universitas Wanita Internasional	51	137	37,23
041048	Universitas Mandiri	59	218	27,06
041054	Universitas Nahdlatul Ulama Cirebon	74	178	41,57
041037	Universitas Al-Ghifari	61	103	59,22
043018	Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Ekonomi Tridharma	24	68	35,29
043022	Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Ekonomi Ekuitas	57	100	57,00
043071	STMIK Likmi	14	44	31,82
043243	STMIK LPKIA Bandung	11	29	37,93
043111	STKIP Arrahmaniyah	28	80	35,00
043036	STKIP PGRI Sukabumi	15	31	48,39
043107	Sekolah Tinggi Teknologi Texmaco	7	40	17,50
043040	Sekolah Tinggi Teknologi Mandala	32	81	39,51
045016	Politeknik TEDC	65	164	39,63
045019	Politeknik Gunakarya Indonesia Bekasi	0	32	0,00
045037	Politeknik Triguna Tasikmalaya	14	25	56,00
045033	Politeknik Kesehatan Bhakti Pertiwi Husada Bekasi	8	31	25,81
045022	Politeknik Agroindustri Subang	1	30	3,33
042005	Institut Teknologi Sains Bandung	42	95	44,21
042006	Institut Teknologi Harapan Bangsa	36	62	58,06
0212003	Institut Agama Islam Latifah Mubarakiyah Suryalaya	24	63	38,10

0212024	Institut Agama Islam Shalahuddin Al-Ayyubi Tambun	0	23	0,00
0212028	Institut Agama Islam Al Zaytun Indonesia	5	35	14,29
0213125	STAI PERSIS Bandung	8	44	18,18
0213021	STAI Bhakti Persada Majalaya Bandung	2	32	6,25
0213149	STAI YAMISA Soreang	3	34	8,82
0213150	STAI YAPATA Al - Jawami Bandung	5	23	21,74

Based on table 1 above, it is known that the level of lecturer participation in several Private Universities (Region IV) in the field of research and community service is still not optimal. It can be seen that there are still many whose achievements are below 50%, and some are even still Zero in the field of research and community service, as happened to the Politeknik Gunakarya Indonesia Bekasi dan Institut Agama Islam Shalahuddin Al-Ayyubi Tambun. Ideally, the number of lecturers registered in PDDIKTI is the same as the Verified Authors in SINTA, meaning that all lecturers have implemented the Tri Dharma of Higher Education in the field of research and community service. In relation to community service, Susi Adiauwaty (2020) in *ESENSI: Journal of Business Management*, Vol. 23 No. 2/2020 stated that lecturers' commitment to the aspect of community service as one of the Tri Dharmas that must be done is still low.

Coaching is an effective approach to develop skills, improve performance, and help human resources (HR) find solutions to various challenges. Coaching empowers individuals to experience learning, personal growth, and performance improvement. According to the Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development (CIPD), coaching aims to improve optimal performance by focusing on specific skills and goals and impacting personality aspects such as social interaction and confidence. Research shows that integrated coaching can improve participants' knowledge and skills, self-awareness and behavior as found by Makmun Abdullah (2020) and Kombarakarn et al. (2008). Coaching also boosts confidence, contribution to the company and team performance and helps prioritize business opportunities and implement high-impact projects.

The purpose of this study is to develop and test the effectiveness of the Integrated Coaching Model in improving the performance of lecturers in private universities, especially the Universitas Komputer Indonesia dan Universitas Garut. This research focuses on how a comprehensive and systematic coaching approach can affect aspects of lecturer performance, including teaching ability, research productivity and academic contribution. By implementing an integrated coaching model, it is hoped that an effective method can be found in supporting the professional development of lecturers so that it ultimately contributes to improving the quality of education in private universities.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Management Theory

The management theory that is the basis of this study is more oriented to the scientific management theory (Scientific Management) proposed by Nickels, McHugh and McHugh (1997) in Nashar (2013:9) stating that management is "The process used to accomplish

organizational goals through planning, organizing, directing, and controlling people and other organizational resources" (a process carried out to realize organizational goals through a series of activities in the form of planning, organizing, directing and controlling people and other organizational resources).

Coaching Theory

The coaching theory that is the basis for this study uses the theory put forward by Jonathan Passmore (2019:2) that the Integrated Coaching model is "bringing together different approaches to create a coherent way of working, while having the flexibility to adapt to different coaches".

The goal of coaching is to foster relationships in the organization, the coach and the person being coached, and involves an approach tailored to suit the client. Coaching is often used to help individuals as they prepare for or move on to a new task, improve work habits, adapt to a changing environment or overcome certain obstacles. So that coaching can be an effective tool in meeting various organizational needs.

Coaching provides strategic guidance for a person on how to reach their full potential to achieve career goals. Basically, coaching helps a person to understand what their strengths are and what still needs to be improved to improve their professional abilities even better, as a leader for themselves, as a human learner, adjusting to the current situation to continue to grow and develop, and actualizing their ideas and ideas.

Performance Theory

For the performance theory used in this study, it refers to the theory expressed by Bernardin and Russel (1993:379) in Syafri & Alwi (2014:72) in their book entitled "Human Resource Management in Public Organizations" reveals that performance is as a report of results obtained on a certain job function or activity carried out during a certain period of time.

According to Mitchell (quoted by Sedarmayanti, 2009:51) in his book "Human Resources and Work Productivity," there are several important employee performance indicators: Work Quality, which includes the achievement of work according to the requirements of high suitability and readiness, as well as contributing to the progress of the organization through the improvement of knowledge and skills. Punctuality, which is the suitability of the completion time of work with the planned target, to ensure that it does not interfere with other work. Initiative, where high-performing employees always have smart ideas and are able to adapt to change. Ability, which reflects competence in carrying out tasks. Finally, Communication, which involves interaction with both superiors and stakeholders, so that good cooperation is created and the organization's vision, mission, and goals are achieved.

RESEARCH METHODS

The method applied in this study is qualitative research with a case study approach. As Moleong (2017:6) states that qualitative methods are research methods that intend to understand the phenomenon of what is experienced by the research subject such as behavior,

perception, motivation, action and others holistically and by way of description in the form of words and language, in a special context that is natural by utilizing various natural methods. This approach was chosen because each process is carried out in detail, sharpness, and depth (Fadillah, 2022). Then case study research is a type of qualitative research where researchers conduct in-depth exploration of programs, events, processes, activities, on one or more people carried out in detail to obtain accurate data.

Data was collected through a variety of qualitative techniques, including in-depth interviews, participant observations, and document analysis. Interviews were conducted with lecturers, study program heads, and university management to get a comprehensive overview of the implementation and impact of the integrated coaching model. Participant observation allows researchers to see firsthand the coaching process and interactions that occur and identify factors that support or hinder the success of the model. Document analysis involves examining reports, policies, and other documentation relevant to the lecturer coaching program.

The data analysis in this study is inductive, which means that the researcher builds an understanding and conclusion from the collected data without applying a rigid theoretical framework or initial hypothesis. Through thematic analysis, data obtained from interviews, observations, and documents are analyzed to identify patterns, themes, and categories that arise naturally from the data. This process begins with open coding, where data is encoded into smaller units of meaning, then continues with the grouping of these codes into broader, abstract themes. The inductive approach allows researchers to remain open to the various possibilities and interpretations that arise from the data, to produce a rich and in-depth understanding of the effectiveness of the integrated coaching model in improving the performance of lecturers in the private universities studied.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Result

1. Universitas Komputer Indonesia (Unikom)

a. Integrated Coaching Model Planning (Unikom)

Strategic planning at Unikom is prepared by the rectorate leadership and outlined in the Development Master Plan (RIP) document based on the feasibility study. The stages of RIP preparation involve setting Unikom's future goals, formulating a strategy to achieve the Tri Dharma of Higher Education and determining the resources needed, with the participation of the rectorate, faculty deans, and the science & technology foundation. The RIP document includes an introduction, Unikom profile, SWOT analysis, development direction map, basic strategies and policies, performance indicators, and implementation design, and was ratified through a Decision Letter. Unikom's Strategic Plan (Renstra) document, which is valid for five years, explains decision-making strategies and provides a basic framework for other planning with a drafting stage involving the rectorate and directorate leaders. The 2021-2026 Strategic Plan emphasizes improving the quality of lecturers through coaching and periodic competency improvement. The Annual Work Plan is an elaboration of the Strategic Plan, focusing on human

resource development for lecturers and education staff, and involves the Vice Chancellor II, deans, heads of study programs, and directorate leaders in its preparation. The Integrated Coaching Model at Unikom uses the GROW approach which includes goal identification, reality review, consideration of options, and agreement on action (will) by the coachee.

b. Organizing the Integrated Coaching Model (Unikom)

The allocation of resources at Unikom is focused on using existing assets to achieve goals by considering the cost, time, materials, and tools required. The allocation of human resources and budgets for coaching programs is adjusted to the needs, including cooperation with other universities and consultants for external coaches and the use of competent internal lecturers. The operational procedures of the Integrated Coaching Model program are established to ensure the effectiveness and efficiency of the program, including planning, organizing, directing, and evaluating coaching activities. The determination of procedures is carried out at the beginning of the academic year in line with the annual work plan and the issues of the Tri Dharma of Higher Education. Lecturer development programs through coaching are carried out by various parties at Unikom, such as study programs, the directorate of P3M and the directorate of journals & scientific publications. The organizational structure of the coaching program is explained to ensure a clear division of responsibilities and tasks with the management of the program being regulated by the study program for teaching and by the Directorate of P3M for research and service. A good structure is expected to improve the performance of human resources in accordance with the PIQIE cultural values applied at Unikom.

c. Integrated Coaching Model (Unikom) Briefing

In the implementation of the directing coaching program, Unikom leaders, including the rector, provide direction, guidance, and initiatives to their subordinates and ensure harmonious coordination in the work environment. This directing process is prepared and implemented according to planning which includes the stages of identifying coaching needs, determining goals and objectives, determining success criteria, and the methods used. Identifying the need to focus on lecturer performance issues related to government regulations, national and internal phenomena, as well as problems faced by Unikom lecturers. The goals and objectives of the program are determined by the program manager, such as the study program or the Directorate of P3M related to the Tri Dharma of Higher Education. The success criteria are based on the suitability of planning, communication between coaches and coachees, and coachee's understanding through pre and post-coaching questionnaires. The coaching method adopts the GROW approach and is adjusted by the coach. The first coaching was held in 2018 at the Unikom Auditorium with experienced external coaches. The Rector of Unikom, Prof. Dr. Ir. H. Eddy Soeryanto Soegoto, MT, provided motivation to encourage the enthusiasm of the coaching participants. The policy of lecturer participation in coaching is contained in the rectorate's circular letter aimed at lecturers who are not optimal in carrying out the Tri Dharma of Higher Education duties so that their potential develops and their performance increases so that it has an impact on increasing the IKU of Higher Education.

d. Integrated Coaching Model Supervision (Unikom)

In implementing the supervisory function, Unikom always evaluates each of its activities to determine the level of effectiveness. This evaluation aims to improve the quality of future activities and provide recommendations for decision-making. The evaluation of the activity was carried out by the Directorate of Quality Assurance led by Assoc. Prof. Dr. Siti Kurnia Rahayu, S.E., M.Ak., Ak, CA, including the evaluation of lecturers' performance every semester in teaching, research, and community service after participating in coaching. Information systems that support evaluation include sister.ristekdikti.go.id, sinta2.ristekdikti.go.id, garuda.ristekdikti.go.id, and bima.kemdikbud.go.id pages. The performance evaluation stages start from determining the topic, evaluation method, implementation, data analysis, to the preparation of recommendations. Supervision of coaching programs is carried out through clarification and correction, with a pattern of multi-level clarification and corrective actions carried out if necessary.

e. Supporting Factors and Factors Hindering Management Integrated Coaching Model (Unikom)

In the implementation of the Integrated Coaching Model at Unikom, there are supporting and inhibiting factors. Unikom lecturers really appreciate coaching activities that are considered helpful and motivate to improve their performance. The institution's support can be seen from the presence of experienced resource persons and the budget that is always provided for coaching activities, as well as space facilities and supporting equipment. Unikom also makes coaching a flagship program that is routinely carried out and contained in the RKT document. However, there are obstacles such as budget mismatches that have an impact on the implementation of group coaching, as well as a lack of time and perception that coaching is only for problematic lecturers. In addition, post-coaching supervision and evaluation face obstacles in updating information about lecturer productivity, especially in research and community service.

f. Efforts to Overcome Obstacles in Integrated Coaching Model Management (Unikom)

In the implementation of coaching activities at Unikom, managers often face obstacles that are overcome with certain strategies. For the problem of inconsistency in the group coaching budget, the manager conducts participant efficiency and priority based on coordination with the Head of the Study Program. For HR briefing, awareness of the importance of coaching is increased and the negative perception that coaching is only for problematic lecturers is eliminated, emphasizing that coaching helps develop the potential of lecturers. In supervision, evaluations are carried out through periodic coordination with lecturer performance information system operators such as Sister PT, BIMA, SINTA, GARUDA, and ANJANI. For lecturers who do not have time due to clashing schedules, Unikom holds a hybrid program, allowing lecturers to take part in online coaching and manage schedules flexibly. Unikom also recruits competent internal lecturers as coaches to overcome budget problems. Unikom's policy includes human resource development in the Annual Work Plan of Study Programs, and in the field of research, the rectorate issues an appeal for lecturers to participate in coaching,

especially for those who receive grants or off-campus assistance such as the MBKM and PKM research assistance programs in 2021.

g. Work Results of Lecturers of the Universitas Komputer Indonesia (Unikom) after the Implementation of the *Integrated Coaching Model*

After participating in the Integrated Coaching Model activity, Unikom lecturers showed a significant improvement in productivity and work quality, especially in the implementation of the Tri Dharma of Higher Education. In 2021, Unikom managed to obtain a research and service grant of 1.3 billion rupiah from the Directorate General of Higher Education and Technology thanks to its success in implementing the 8 Main Work Indicator (IKU) criteria of the Independent Learning Independent Campus (MBKM) program. The real contribution of lecturers can be seen from the increase in the institution's accreditation ranking, the acquisition of various national and international awards, and the achievement of Unikom as one of the best private universities in Indonesia.

The productivity of Unikom lecturers in the field of education and teaching has also increased, marked by an increase in the number of lecturers with the functional positions of Professor, Head Lector, Lector, and Expert Assistant. Unikom lecturers consistently report performance burdens through sister.ristekdikti.go.id showing their ability to manage the teaching and learning process and student guidance. The quality of lecturers' work is reflected in the publication of research and service articles in national and international journals as well as the activeness of lecturers as speakers in various important activities including those held by the Ministry of Education and Culture and other international forums.

The initiative of Unikom lecturers in reporting duties and responsibilities as well as in carrying out research and service, shows the positive impact of the Integrated Coaching Model. Cooperation between lecturers, both national and international, is increasing with collaboration in research and other scientific activities such as those carried out with the Japan Advanced Institute of Science and Technology (JAIST) and several universities in ASEAN. In addition, Unikom lecturers managed to solve problems faced in their assignments, through root cause analysis and the implementation of effective solution strategies (CL, B, C, Doc).

2. University of Garut (Uniga)

a. Planning (Uniga)

Universitas Garut (Uniga) develops a sustainable program to achieve its goals as a Private University which is based on the Development Master Plan (RIP) document as a strategic and technical guideline. RIP Uniga is prepared with the participation of rectorate leaders, faculties and study programs covering the 2020-2045 period and aims to improve the performance, career, and competitiveness of lecturers.

The implementation of RIP is supported by a Strategic Plan (Renstra) document, prepared every five years with a strategy to achieve the desired results by involving leadership elements at various levels. Lecturer development through coaching is also a focus in the Strategic Plan which emphasizes improving the quality of lecturers' work in a sustainable manner. In addition,

Uniga's Annual Work Plan (RKT) describes the goals and programs of the Strategic Plan which are dynamically prepared based on evaluation and focus on improving the quality of lecturers in implementing the Tri Dharma of Higher Education. The coaching approach in RKT uses the TIRTA method (main objectives, identification, action plans, and responsibilities) which is applied in several study programs to develop lecturers and achieve Uniga's vision, mission, and goals.

b. Organizing the Integrated Coaching Model (Uniga)

Organizing at the University of Garut (Uniga) is an important management function that includes the allocation and merger of resources to achieve the goals of the university. In its implementation, aspects such as resources, operational procedures, and organizational structure greatly support the success of the established program. Resources at Uniga include people and budgets with the rectorate supporting the improvement of lecturer performance through various developments. In the coaching program, the rectorate seeks to support the maximum aspects of the budget and human resources, coordinating with faculties and study programs. For effectiveness and efficiency, Uniga establishes coaching operational procedures that are tailored by program creators in the fields of teaching, research, and community service. The organizational structure of the coaching program management is led by the head of the study program, the head of the Research Institute (Lemlit), and the head of the Community Service Institute (LPM), all of which are determined directly by the Rector of Uniga.

c. Briefing Integrated Coaching Model (Uniga)

The success of the University of Garut (Uniga) in implementing the Integrated Coaching Model is achieved by focusing on improving the efficiency and activities of existing resources and referring to the Strategic Plan and RKT documents. In identifying coaching needs, managers study the condition of lecturers to ensure targeted and evaluative coaching goals. The criteria for coaching success include improving individual and university performance, lecturer work productivity, and lecturer motivation, creativity, and innovation.

The program, started in 2022, uses the TIRTA method (main objectives, identification, action plan, and responsibilities) and includes activities such as "Coaching Clinic Service Research Proposal" with experienced lecturer and coach participants. Motivation is given by Uniga's leadership, supported by incentives, additional teaching hours, and special recommendations. Policies for career development and improvement of lecturer performance are regulated through the Rector's Decree and Circular Letter, including the improvement of four lecturer competencies, research activities, and community service, with evaluations and warning letters for lecturers who have not shown improvement.

d. Supervision of the Integrated Coaching Model (Uniga)

The implementation of the supervisory function after the implementation of the Integrated Coaching Model at the University of Garut (Uniga) is carried out through evaluation to measure the success of the activity. The evaluation is carried out by Study Programs, Research Institutes (Lemlit), and Community Service Institutes (LPM) using clear and objective parameters. The

evaluation stages include the reactions of coaching participants, the implementation of sessions, participant behavior, and coaching results, which are measured through questionnaires or Google Forms. Monitoring the improvement of lecturer performance after coaching is also carried out by looking at the results of lecturers' achievements in learning, research, community service, and administrative tasks. Clarification was carried out for lecturers who have not shown performance improvement to understand the obstacles faced. Although the supervisory function includes corrective actions, until now Uniga has not carried out post-coaching corrective actions because no irregularities have occurred.

e. Supporting Factors and Hindering Factors of Management Integrated Coaching Model (Uniga)

Uniga has provided various forms of support for the implementation of the Integrated Coaching Model for lecturers, including cooperation with the National Certification Agency (BNSP) for the provision of coaches, development program budgets, and rooms or halls for coaching clinics. Universitas Garut has four campus locations that support this activity. The institution through the rectorate is committed to realizing coaching activities for the sake of improving lecturer performance and providing incentives for lecturers' achievements in national and international scientific publications. However, there are obstacles in the aspect of human resources, especially the participation of lecturers who have difficulty managing time due to the busyness of teaching and guiding students, especially for coaching activities that are carried out offline.

f. Efforts to Overcome Obstacles in the Management Integrated Coaching Model (Uniga)

Uniga has taken concrete steps to overcome obstacles in the implementation of the Integrated Coaching Model by issuing a circular through the study program for lecturers to participate in coaching activities, coordinate with academics to find out lecturers' teaching schedules, and shift some coaching activities from offline to online using applications such as Zoom and Google Meet. For lecturers who are unable to attend, Uniga provides independent coaching sessions with coaches from BNSP, as long as the lecturer submits a schedule of willingness first. In addition, Uniga issued a policy in the form of an appeal to study programs to include coaching activities in the annual work plan as an effort to develop lecturers, as well as issuing a Rector's Decree on incentives for lecturers who publish scientific articles in reputable journals indexed by Scopus and SINTA, with a nominal incentive based on publication rankings.

g. Work Results of Lecturers of the University of Garut (Uniga) after the Implementation of the Integrated Coaching Model

The productivity of Uniga lecturers increased significantly after participating in the Integrated Coaching Model activity. In 2023, Uniga is included in the top 5 private universities that receive the most research grants in the LLDIKTI IV (West Java-Banten) region, along with several other universities. The data on the sinta.kemdikbud.go.id page shows that the number of Uniga lecturers recorded is 269 people, with a significant total of scientific publications on various platforms. Academic productivity can also be seen from the increase in the number of lecturers with functional positions, as well as the increase in the number of textbooks,

references, and monographs produced by Uniga lecturers. The improvement in the quality of work of Uniga lecturers in implementing the Tri Dharma of Higher Education can be seen from pedagogic competence and creativity in teaching and learning activities. Uniga lecturers are also active in reporting the results of learning, research, and community service through the *Sister.kemendikbuddikti* platform. Many lecturers were invited as resource persons in various training events, seminars, and technical guidance, showing recognition for their competence. Uniga lecturers also show high initiative in finding strategies to meet their workload, such as participation in MBKM programs and scientific publications in reputable journals.

After the Integrated Coaching Model activity, cooperation between Uniga lecturers increased in planning and implementing the Tri Dharma of Higher Education. This collaboration includes research, community service, and publication of scientific papers, which results in patents. Uniga lecturers also show the ability to solve problems through self-evaluation and coordination with related parties to find solutions. This strong initiative and cooperation contributes to improving the overall performance of Uniga lecturers, both in academic and administrative aspects (CL, A, B, C, Doc).

Discussion

Effective human resource management has become crucial in the face of increasing pressure and competition in various organizations, including Higher Education institutions. One approach that has proven effective is coaching, which helps develop the potential and improve the professional abilities of lecturers. Coaching provides strategic guidance to achieve career goals by strengthening creative partnership relationships between coaches and the individuals they coach. The results of the analysis show that the Integrated Coaching Model has succeeded in improving the performance of lecturers at the Universitas Komputer Indonesia (Unikom) and Universitas Garut (Uniga), as evidenced by the increase in productivity, work quality, initiatives, cooperation, and solutions in facing the challenges faced.

The PIQIE culture applied at Unikom and Uniga's commitment to life values emphasizes the importance of integrity, professionalism, and excellence in every aspect of activities, including coaching and improving lecturer performance. The principles of the Six Value Systems, such as faith, science, and charity, also guide the implementation of coaching by emphasizing good communication, regular evaluation, and holistic improvement of human resource capabilities in accordance with the values believed and applied in the context of higher education.

a. Planning

Planning is the first and most important managerial function that provides the basis for other functions of management, such as organizing, directing, and supervising. In Higher Education, this planning is outlined in the Development Master Plan (RIP), which includes academic and non-academic planning and is integrated in the Tri Dharma of Higher Education. RIP is elaborated into a Strategic Plan (Renstra), which serves as a basic benchmark for determining the direction and strategy of the institution, and is then detailed in the Annual Work Plan which explains how to implement the strategic plan in short-term achievements. The planning refers to the Indonesian Minister of Education and Culture Number 22 of 2020 which encourages

lecturer performance to produce quality research, in line with the goals of the program to improve the quality of lecturers and education staff.

If it is related to the theological aspect, that humans can only plan, but God is the one who prescribes. Allah's destiny and plan include two things, namely *qada* which is certainty, measure, satisfaction, or the manifestation of the will. And *qadar* is the manifestation of the will of Allah Subhanahu Wa Ta'ala towards all His creatures in a certain size and form.

In relation to the philosophical aspect, planning is a comprehensive formulation process based on ontological, epistemology, and axiological aspects that can outline several important components, namely; What goals to achieve, how to carry out actions to realize the goals, and when, when and when these actions are to be carried out. So the desired result of the planning process is to present an important document that is useful for an organization. Philosophy in a strategic plan contains elements, such as; vision, mission, goals, objectives, policies, programs and activities that are realistic by anticipating future developments.

In the concept of the Six Value Systems, the implementation of the planning process is included in the theological, logical-rational and teleological aspects, because in the realization of planning must be far-sighted (visionary) by prioritizing logic, clarity and reality that occurs, so that the planning made is in accordance with its function, integrated and productive, as well as effective and efficient.

Based on the discussion above, it can be concluded that the planning to improve the performance of good and optimal lecturers of private universities is prepared based on the planning theory of Nickels, McHugh and McHugh and is supported by the theological, logical-rational and teleological values of Islam sourced from the Qur'an and Hadith.

b. Organizing

Organizing has a very vital function in the management system because it is the main mechanism for leaders to mobilize all resources to achieve the goals of the university. According to Schermerhorn (1996:218), organizing is the process of organizing people and other resources to work towards a common goal. This involves the preparation and division of duties and responsibilities to each work unit based on its function in the organization, providing clear direction on each activity, and improving the abilities and knowledge of each member of the organization effectively and efficiently. A good organization implements its functions and authorities with a division of duties and responsibilities in accordance with the capacity of its members.

The coaching program at Unikom appears in the annual work plan detailed by each study program through the creation of a Roadmap to improve lecturer performance. The organization and determination of resources are carried out according to the needs of the program, both from the human and budget aspects. The organizational concept applied includes resource allocation, formulation and assignment of tasks, and placement of human resources in the right positions. The determination of coaching program procedures is carried out based on issues that develop in the current academic year. Coaching programs related to teaching are managed by the Study

Program, while research and service are managed by the Directorate of P3M. At the University of Garut (Uniga), the rectorate's support in improving lecturer performance includes aspects of human resources and budget. The Integrated Development Model at Uniga was initiated by Research Institutes and Community Service Institutions, in collaboration with study programs. The management of the coaching program is determined by the rector of Uniga, ensuring the availability of the management team to create cooperation and responsibility in their duties.

Organizing in Islam is not only about structure, but also about doing work neatly with Islamic values such as sincerity, togetherness, and sacrifice. Surah As-Saff Verse 4 in the Qur'an teaches the importance of cohesiveness, discipline, and cooperation to achieve a common goal, similar to striving in the way of Allah. In an ontological perspective, organizing is where people come together to achieve a common goal, while epistemology emphasizes that the success of an organization depends on the cooperation of its members and that failure is caused by negative internal factors. Axiology focuses on values and norms in organizations such as honesty, justice, and kindness. In conclusion, the organization to improve the performance of lecturers in Private Universities must be based on the theory of Nickels, McHugh, and McHugh, and supported by Islamic ethical-legal, aesthetic, physical-physiological, and teleological values sourced from the Qur'an and Hadith.

c. Directing

Directing is a managerial function that increases the effectiveness and efficiency of performance and creates a dynamic work environment. This function ensures coordination in each section, so that harmonization is created in the work environment. Activities in the direction function include the implementation of the coaching process, leadership, assignment assignments, motivation, and regular explanations of work and organizational policies. At Unikom and Uniga, the direction function is comprehensive and continuous, implemented at every level of management of managers. At Unikom, briefings are carried out on an ongoing basis by leaders through faculties, study programs, and directorates. There are two forms of coaching: One on One Coaching and Group Coaching, starting with the identification of lecturer needs by the program manager.

In carrying out the direction, each leader is responsible to their subordinates to complete the work at each level of management. The identification of coaching needs at Uniga refers to the RIP and Strategic Plan documents as well as higher education issues. The success of the program is seen from the output of the lecturers, and if there is no improvement, a warning letter is given. The coaching method is left to the coach, with the motivation of the program manager. The concept of briefing is in line with the opinion of Nickels, McHugh, and McHugh, that good briefing involves effective leadership and motivation. In an organization, direction is carried out through rules that all elements follow, with the leader setting an example of behavior. In Arabic, the briefing is known as "al-taujih," which is described in the Qur'an surah Al-Kahf Verse 2.

Verses in the Qur'an show that directing is an important part of management, which must be done by leaders to create cooperation in achieving organizational goals. In addition to providing

briefings, leaders must also appreciate successes and warn of potential failures if activities are not carried out as planned. In the concept of the Six Value Systems, direction in human resource development through coaching requires attitudes such as coordination, communication, initiative, patience, sincerity, courtesy, honesty, love, stimulus, guidance, good work on tasks, harmonization, sustainability, usefulness, and comprehensiveness. These attitudes reflect theological, ethical-legal, physical-physiological, aesthetic, and teleological values. In conclusion, the direction action to improve the performance of lecturers in private universities is good and optimal based on the theory of direction from Nickels, McHugh, and McHugh, and is supported by Islamic theological, ethical-legal, physical-physiological, aesthetic, and teleological values sourced from the Qur'an and Hadith.

d. Supervision (*CONTROLLING*)

Supervision (controlling) is a management function that aims to evaluate organizational performance based on established standards and make improvements when necessary. Supervisory activities include evaluation of the achievement of goals and targets, clarification and correction of deviations, and solutions to problems that arise. Supervision is carried out in three stages: initially, to monitor technical aspects; middle, for assistance and monitoring of progress and obstacles; and finally, to evaluate the overall activities so that improvements can be made in the future.

In general, supervision at Unikom and Uniga Private Universities in the implementation of coaching activities is appropriate, objective, and comprehensive. This is in accordance with good supervision indicators according to Handoko (2015), including aspects of accuracy, timeliness, focus on strategic points, objectivity, economy, organizational, coordination, flexibility, and operability. At Unikom, the evaluation of coaching programs is carried out by the Directorate of Quality Assurance and the supervision of lecturer performance is carried out on an ongoing basis every semester. At Uniga, the program evaluation method uses a questionnaire and the results are reported to the relevant parties. If it is found that lecturers with performance have not improved, clarification is carried out to identify and overcome the obstacles faced. Until now, the correction stage has not been needed because there are no lecturers who need this action.

From a theological point of view, supervision in Islam aims to correct what is not right, correct what is wrong, and justify the right, so that every activity runs according to expectations. Humans are believed to be watched over by angels who record all their actions, both visible and hidden, as stated in the Qur'an, surah Al-Infitar verses 10-12. If associated with the concept of the Six Value Systems, supervision in coaching activities requires an honest and courteous attitude (theological), helpful and coordinated (teleological), timely and flexible (logical-rational), as well as objective and responsible (ethical-legal), and comprehensive and accurate (physical-physiological). Based on this discussion, supervision in improving the optimal performance of lecturers in private universities is compiled based on the supervision theory from Nickels, McHugh, and McHugh, and is supported by Islamic physical-physiological values sourced from the Qur'an and Hadith.

e. Supporting Factors and Inhibiting Factors in Integrated Coaching Model Management in Private Universities (Universitas Komputer Indonesia dan Universitas Garut)

Human resource management in higher education is essential to strengthen work culture and achieve institutional goals. This management includes development through coaching activities, which are effective, efficient, and easy to implement in various places with different focuses. Coaching helps overcome obstacles and utilizes supporting factors, such as the provision of experienced resource persons, funding, facilities, and commitment from the university. However, obstacles such as budget mismatches, surveillance issues, and data synchronization remain and require special attention.

The Universitas Komputer Indonesia (Unikom) fully supports the implementation of the Integrated Coaching Model, providing the necessary human resources, budget, and facilities. Evaluation of coaching programs is carried out by the Directorate of Quality Assurance with non-test evaluation instruments such as interviews, questionnaires, and observations. However, obstacles such as budget inconsistencies and problems in evaluating lecturer productivity are still challenges. On the other hand, the University of Garut (Uniga) also supports the career development of lecturers through collaboration with the National Professional Certification Agency (BNSP) and provides facilities and incentives for scientific publications. However, the busyness of lecturers and the lack of motivation in more senior lecturers are obstacles.

Based on research and implementation at Unikom and Uniga, supporting factors such as adequate facilities and infrastructure, good cooperation, and clear procedures are very helpful in the implementation of coaching. However, obstacles such as time adjustments, long implementation periods, and lack of records of previous activity processes remain challenges. This management process reflects theological and logical-rational values, and shows that support and obstacles are part of qodarulloh that must be faced with istiqomah. In conclusion, the management of the Integrated Coaching Model is very effective in improving the performance of lecturers in private universities by paying attention to the existing supporting and inhibiting factors.

f. Efforts to Overcome Obstacles in Integrated Coaching Model Management in Private Universities (Universitas Komputer Indonesia dan Universitas Garut)

Every activity in an organization must face various obstacles, both internal and external. Organizations must work to overcome these obstacles in order to survive, compete, and thrive on purpose. Universitas Computer-Indonesia (Unikom) overcomes obstacles in the implementation of the Integrated Coaching Model with several strategies such as adjusting the needs of activities, periodic coordination with lecturer performance information system operators, establishing communication with competent internal lecturers as coaches, and including lecturer career development activities in the strategic plan. In addition, they encourage the participation of lecturers, especially those who receive grant programs, in coaching activities. The University of Garut (Uniga) also faces obstacles in the implementation of the Integrated Coaching Model and overcoming problems with various strategies and

policies. This includes making circulars from study programs to participate in coaching, increasing lecturer motivation through schedule coordination, shifting coaching activities online using applications such as Google Meet, and separating strategic and technical decisions at the institutional level. In addition, they issue policies to incentivize lecturers who publish scientific articles. Efforts to overcome these obstacles reflect the theological value of trusting in God for the effort made and discipline as part of the physical-physiological value. Both universities are committed to overcoming obstacles in the management of the Integrated Coaching Model to improve optimal lecturer performance, in accordance with Islamic values sourced from the Qur'an and Hadith.

g. Results of Lecturers' Work in Private Universities (Universitas Komputer Indonesia dan Universitas Garut (Uniga) After the Implementation of the Integrated Coaching Model

As a result of the work of lecturers in higher education, the assessment of success depends only on the quantity but also the quality of the implementation of their duties and responsibilities, including in terms of education, research, and community service. Before the coaching program, the performance of lecturers at the Universitas Komputer Indonesia (Unikom) and Universitas Garut (Uniga) was not optimal, especially in the aspects of research, community service, and scientific publications. Factors such as tight schedules, lack of self-confidence, and human resource management that has not been maximized, and lecturer competence are the causes. However, with the implementation of the Integrated Coaching Model, there has been a significant increase in productivity, quality, initiative, teamwork, and problem-solving skills.

The work results of lecturers in private universities, as observed at Unikom and Uniga, vary greatly because they are influenced by the ability and expertise of each lecturer in carrying out their duties. Research by Mustafa and Chiang shows that a lecturer's performance is influenced by his or her abilities and attitudes, which can be evaluated through a comparison between the two. Lecturer performance assessment standards are governed by ministerial laws and regulations, emphasizing four main competencies: pedagogic, professional, personal, and social. The coaching activities implemented by Unikom and Uniga aim to optimize the potential of lecturers in all aspects of the tridharma of higher education, reflecting efforts to meet national standards in education.

From a theological perspective, the concept of performance emphasizes self-actualization which describes a person's efforts to optimize their potential in achieving life goals. This is in accordance with the teachings of Islam which encourages every individual to work well and direct his efforts clearly and dedicatedly. The hadith narrated by Thabrani emphasizes the importance of the quality of work that is directed and full of sincerity, where Allah Subhanahu Wa Ta'ala appreciates His servants who try well. In the context of the Six Life Value Systems, the role of lecturers as educators, researchers, devotees, administrators, leaders, innovators, and motivators, if done properly and sincerely, reflects theological and ethical-legal values. The work of lecturers who are focused, directed, and thorough also reflects logical-rational values, while the attitude of realizing and utilizing one's potential describes physical-physiological

values. Thus, the implementation of the Integrated Coaching Model can effectively improve the performance of lecturers in private universities, supported by the principles of Islamic values sourced from the Qur'an and Hadith.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that the Integrated Coaching Model Management in improving the performance of lecturers at Private Universities has been in accordance with the management functions of Nickels, McHugh and McHugh and is based on the value system (Achmad Sanusi), so that it has produced lecturers who have good and optimal performance at the Universitas Komputer Indonesia dan Universitas Garut. In addition, the special conclusion of this dissertation highlights the essential, substantial, and meaningful aspects of the findings of the research results related to the implementation of the Integrated Coaching Model in improving the performance of lecturers in private universities (PTS). Good and optimal planning is prepared in a visionary manner, prioritizing logic, clarity, and reality, supported by Islamic theological, logical-rational, and teleological values sourced from the Qur'an and Hadith, as stated in the planning theory of Nickels, McHugh, and McHugh. Organizing is neat, well, and correctly arranged based on the organizing theory of the same experts, supported by Islamic ethical-legal, aesthetic, physical-physiological, and teleological values. Briefings are carried out in a coordinated, communicative, and continuous manner with the support of Islamic theological, ethical-legal, physical-physiological, aesthetic, and teleological values, based on the theory of direction from Nickels, McHugh, and McHugh. Supervision is arranged in a continuous, useful, comprehensive, and accurate manner in accordance with the supervision theory of these experts and supported by Islamic physical-physiological values.

The supporting and inhibiting factors of the Integrated Coaching Model management are identified based on aspects of human resources, budget plans, infrastructure, and commitment to realizing the program. To overcome these obstacles, strategies are prepared, ideas are made, and policies are carried out with the support of Islamic physical-physiological values. The results of the lecturers' work after the implementation of the Integrated Coaching Model showed an increase in work productivity, work quality, initiative, and cooperation, supported by Islamic theological, ethical-legal, logical-rational, and physical-physiological values sourced from the Qur'an and Hadith. Thus, the implementation of the Integrated Coaching Model has proven to be effective in improving lecturer performance in private universities, providing a significant positive impact on various aspects of lecturer performance and professional development.

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